

European Research Council
Executive Agency

Established by the European Commission

European Research Council (ERC)

ERC Data Management Plan

ERC OPEN RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)

European Research Council

Established by the European Commission

Project Acronym

Project Number

TRANS-3	101076026
---------	-----------

SUMMARY

This is version 1.0 of the DMP for ERC project TRANS-3. The DMP will be updated during the development of the project to account for new data, standards and/or other updates to data management procedures.

The project both utilizes existing data and generate new datasets in the field of genomics and cell biology.

GENERATED DATA

The following table details data types with the most long-term value which are accordingly preserved and shared through external repositories. Data of long-term value for which there is not currently a widely used database compatible with FAIR principles are stored in the Zenodo community TRANS-3 (<https://zenodo.org/communities/trans-3>).

Category	Type	Working format	Preservation format	Metadata standard	Preservation database	Database url	Max expected size
Genomics	Next generation sequencing	fastq	fastq	MINSEQE (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5706412)	ArrayExpress	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/arrayexpress	50 TB
Microscopy	Light microscopy images	czi	OME-zarr	REMBI (DOI: 10.1038/s41592-021-01166-8)	BioImage Archive	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/arrayexpress	100 TB
Software	R code	r	r	NA	GitHub	https://github.com	100 MB
Software	Python code	py	py	NA	GitHub	https://github.com	100 MB
Software	Bash code	sh	sh	NA	GitHub	https://github.com	100 MB
Textual	Preprints	docx	pdf	NA	bioRxiv	https://www.biorxiv.org	100 MB
Textual	Protocols	docx	pdf	NA	protocols.io	https://www.protocols.io	100 MB
Textual	Manuscripts	docx	pdf	NA	IRIS-AperTO	https://iris.unito.it	100 MB

REUSED DATA

The following table reports databases that are most often consulted throughout the project. It is implied that all databases reported in the previous table are also consulted, so these are not repeated below. References to individual datasets from these or other databases are detailed in preprints, protocols and manuscripts.

Category	Type	Database	Database url	Access type	Version
Genomics	Next generation sequencing	Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO)	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/	Open, free	NA
Genomics	Gene sequences	RefSeq	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/refseq/	Open, free	Release 222
Microscopy	Light microscopy images	Image Data Repository (IDR)	https://idr.openmicroscopy.org	Open, free	NA
Software	R code	Bioconductor	https://www.bioconductor.org	Open, free	3.18

ERC OPEN RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)

1. MAKING DATA FINDABLE

Experiment identification

Experimental procedures to generate new datasets are documented through the RSpace ELN (electronic laboratory notebook; <https://www.researchspace.com>), which aims to enable a Data Commons of interoperable research tools that are used across various domains, and facilitate streamlined and machine actionable passage of data and metadata through the various stages of the research lifecycle.

Individual experiments are identified in the ELN by a unique alphanumeric code to identify the researcher (initials, i.e. AB), the project task (sequential three digit numbers, i.e. 001), the project subtask (sequential letters, i.e. A), the experiment type (standard code, i.e. Q for RT-qPCR), and experimental run (sequential numbers, i.e. 1); the resulting experiment ID (i.e. AB001AQ1) is used to label all samples, data, and metadata relative to the experiment.

Unique identifiers

All repositories chosen for data preservation and sharing assign digital object identifiers (DOI) or a permanent accession number (i.e. ArrayExpress, Biolmage Archive).

Metadata

For data types where a community adopted standard exists, metadata meets at least such standards (i.e. MINSEQE for NGS and REMBI for light microscopy images). For data types where such standards do not yet exist, the metadata follows the structure of individual databases.

2. MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

Repositories

Data of long-term value for which a widely used, specific purpose repository exists are preserved and shared within according to the individual repository policies, which all comply with the FAIR principles.

Repository	FAIR policy URL
ArrayExpress	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/help
Biolmage Archive	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biolmage-archive/help-policies/
GitHub	https://docs.github.com/en/site-policy/acceptable-use-policies/github-acceptable-use-policies
bioRxiv	https://www.biorxiv.org/content/about-biorxiv
protocols.io	https://www.protocols.io/help/faq
IRIS-AperTO	https://iris.unito.it/sr/htm/politiche_eng.html

Other data of long-term value but for which no specific repository exist are preserved and shared in the Zenodo community TRANS-3 (<https://zenodo.org/communities/trans-3>).
<https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>

All additional documentation and data generated through the project is stored in an institutional Google Drive cloud.

Access policies

All data will be shared in repositories that provide open and free public access. The project will set the access policy to "open" at the latest at the time of publication of the results.

Published data stored in the institutional Google Drive will be shared upon reasonable request.

Privacy

The data does not pose issues related to privacy.

ERC OPEN RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)

3. MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Controlled vocabularies

Genomics metadata and text reports follow the HGCN (HUGO Gene Nomenclature Committee) standards (<https://www.genenames.org>).

Light microscopy imaging metadata and protocols follow the EDAM-bioimaging ontology (doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1116432.1).

Textual reports take account of the Gene Ontology (<https://geneontology.org>) and KEGG pathway (<https://www.genome.jp/kegg/pathway.html>) databases.

4. INCREASE DATA RE-USE

Readme

The Zenodo community TRANS-3 contains a readme file that is updated with each new data deposition and detail all dataset information including all the documentation needed to understand the data, how they were obtained, and the process. The readme also contains all relevant links to external repositories with the raw data and detailed protocols.

Protocols

Experimental and analytical methods are reported in the metadata (data-dependent, see table for details), protocols (protocols.io), preprints (bioRxiv) and manuscripts (IRIS-AperTO) according to the relative standards.

Data quality

We apply our best efforts towards data quality, reporting the results of quality controls for datasets where such tools exist (i.e. FASTQC for NGS data). Nevertheless, all information is provided "as-is", and the user shall hold TRANS-3 project members and the host institution free and harmless in connection with the use of such information.

License

Raw data is licensed under CC0.

Analyzed/interpreted data, including textual outputs such as preprints, protocols, and manuscripts, are licensed under CC-BY.

Regardless of the licensing terms, published data should be acknowledged by citing the appropriate preprint, protocol or manuscript. Unpublished data should be acknowledged as it follows:

"[the data] was generated as part of the European Research Council project TRANS-3 (project number: 101076026, PI: Alessandro Bertero) and is available at [repository information]"

ERC OPEN RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)

5. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES and DATA SECURITY

Costs

At this time no costs are foreseen for the preservation of data in public repositories as these are core funded and do not currently impose a limit on dataset size or, in the case of Zenodo, which has a 50 GB limit per dataset, to the number of datasets.

DMP support costs are covered in-kind by the Open Science Unit at the University of Turin.

Infrastructure costs (i.e. institutional cloud storage on Google Drive) are covered in kind by the host institution, University of Turin.

Backups

Newly generated data are stored either on the cloud through the institutional Google Drive, or on local hard drives where cloud storage is unpractical due to the file size (i.e. large NGS and light microscopy images). In this second scenario all data is immediately backed up on at least two hard drives and deposited to a public repository as soon as data quality has been established.

Data lifetime

The lifetime of data preserved in public repositories is the lifetime of the repositories themselves, and all are chosen ensure long-term preservation in line with FAIR principles.

Data stored on the institutional Google Drive will be preserved for at least 10 years from the end of the project or the publication relative to said data, whichever comes after.

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

Title: TRANS-3 - Beyond the chromosome: unravelling the interplay between inter-chromosomal genome architecture and mRNA biogenesis

Creator: Elena Giglia

Principal Investigator: Alessandro Bertero

Data Manager: Elena Giglia

Project Administrator: Gabriella Zaccone

Affiliation: University of Torino

Funder: European Research Council (ERC)

Template: ERC DMP

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4919-9087